

CULTiVATE

Food Sharing in Lisbon

Impact report

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Overview

14 Food sharing initiatives mapped in Lisbon

10 Initiatives include redistributing food, saving surplus food from disposal and providing food for those in need

3 Initiatives include cooking and eating together, strengthening social connection and improving nutrition

8 Initiatives include growing food, reducing food costs for participants and for supporting physical and mental wellbeing

7 Initiatives undertake more than one activity around food, contributing to a more circular bioeconomy

Annual estimated FSI impacts in Lisbon from 14 FSIs*

Social	32,453 meals shared	
Economic	13 tonnes of food produced	
Environmental	21,343 tonnes CO ₂ e avoided	
Civic engagement	448 volunteers active	

*Impacts estimated using The Toolshed SIA and the CULTIVATE Food Sharing Map.

Executive Summary

Food Sharing Initiatives (FSIs) support people to grow, cook, eat, and redistribute food together, as well as share knowledge and spaces. They can contribute significantly to more sustainable, resilient, and socially connected urban food systems. Lisbon has an emerging food sharing landscape shown below:

FSIs mapped in Lisbon (2025)

This report presents estimated sustainability impact scenarios for Lisbon, combining a snapshot of results from the automated mapping of FSIs in Lisbon using CULTIVATE's Food Sharing Mapping tool with data from sustainability impact assessments conducted by FSIs. Scenarios provide low, medium and high estimates of sustainability impact at the city scale.

How to use this report

This report can be used to help support transitions to more sustainable food systems in Lisbon. This includes using the report:

- **As an evidence base:** Use these scenarios as a baseline from which to track and monitor FSI sustainability impacts over time.
- **For policy evaluation:** Identify where FSI activities currently take place and where there are gaps in provision to ensure municipal and national food, climate and community goals are met.
- **For goal tracking:** Map contributions from FSIs to the global sustainable development goals and to local food and food waste targets.

Food sharing in Lisbon

Using CULTIVATE's automated Food Sharing Map, FSIs with a digital presence (web, app, social media) were identified and categorised by activity type: Growing; Cooking & Eating; Redistribution; Multifunctional (e.g. engaging in more than one activity). FSIs cluster in inner-city areas such as Arroios, and Areeiro where population density is very high, and there are high levels of social diversity. The cooking and eating initiatives identified are located in the inner city. Most of the growing initiatives are also located in central Lisbon. Such patterns have been identified in other urban locations across Europe.

There are some FSIs located in the northern periphery, around Lumiar and Carnide, focusing on redistribution and growing activities that require space and storage facilities. There are currently no FSIs identified through the Food Sharing Map in western neighbourhoods such as Ajuda and Restelo, where land use and geography influences activities.

Mapping of FSIs is the first phase of the SIA calculation process which is set out below.

City-scale impact estimation

Impacts were calculated using a four-step process:

1. **Map** – Identifying FSIs and classifying them according to their activity type.
2. **Calculate** – Estimating a) the mean average impact estimation per indicator category b) the low impact estimation and c) the high impact estimation, using SIA data from all forms of FSIs across nine European cities, as follows:
 - Growing – tonnes of food produced
 - Cooking and eating – number of meals shared
 - Redistribution – Tonnes of CO₂e avoided
 - All FSIs – Number of volunteers engaged
3. **Scale** – Multiplying the number of FSIs in each activity category by the a) mean average b) lowest and c) highest impact figure from CULTIVATE FSI SIA impact data to generate city-level estimates.
4. **Scenarios** – Illustrating the range of possible outcomes in municipal food sharing activity.

Lisbon impact scenarios

The table below presents the mean, low and high sustainability impact assessment scenarios for Lisbon.

Food sharing activity	Adjusted No. of FSIs	CULTIVATE average impact per FSI	Mean Impact Scenario Lisbon	Low Impact Scenario Lisbon	High Impact Scenario Lisbon	Metric
Growing	n.3.33	4	13	4.5	106	Tonnes food produced
Cooking & Eating	n.2.33	13,908	32,453	117	7,209,533	Meals shared
Redistribution	n.8.33	2,561	21,343	1,067	133,333	Tonnes CO ₂ e avoided
All FSIs	n.14	32	448	273	1,582	Volunteers

These results provide an early indication of the scale of FSI impacts across Lisbon from 14 FSIs that have a digital trace. Expanding reporting practices within existing FSIs would create a broader picture of the sustainability impacts that the FSIs are creating beyond the narrow quantitative categories detailed in the table above. Research shows that FSIs [create impact across a range of social, economic, environmental and governance areas](#) contributing to urban sustainability, food waste reduction, and community resilience. Other FSIs may not have a digital profile or may not have a profile that the mapping tool can access so do not currently appear on the map. These can be manually added if indicated and verified.

Recommendations

FSIs in Lisbon play a vital role in advancing urban sustainability through food for those who can access them. They save and share surplus food, build community, and enhance resilience. Even with preliminary mapping data and limited impact data points from 14 FSIs, their contributions are clear, measurable and meaningful.

Recommendations are to:

1. **Embed data collection** – Use mapping and SIA data to inform policy making. Strengthening data collection will help inform effective, inclusive urban food policy.
2. **Strengthen the FSI ecosystem** – Use data on the distribution of FSIs and compare with the needs of populations to identify areas where FSIs should be supported. Use SIA data to evidence how FSIs can support unmet needs.
3. **Resilience planning** – Integrate FSIs into local food, health, and emergency planning frameworks.
4. **Food waste reduction** - Demonstrate urban-scale contributions to EU food-waste targets from FSIs to track progress toward 30% waste-reduction goals.

If you would like to know more about the method and data underpinning this SIA report, or if you would like to contribute to expanding the food sharing map contact us at: info@sharingsolutions.eu